

TRANSLATION IS AN IMPORTANT PART OF LINGUISTICS

Madina Ildarovna Khannanova

Zarmed University Department of Languages

Bukhara, Uzbekistan +998936512888

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15489654>

Abstract

This article considers translation as an important aspect of linguistics, reveals its role in the transfer of meanings between languages, its impact on the formation of intercultural communication, as well as the importance of translation in the development of national literatures and scientific thought. It is substantiated that translation is not only a linguistic activity, but also a complex cognitive and cultural process that contributes to the deepening of understanding of languages and cultures.

Key words: translation, linguistics, intercultural communication, linguistic picture of the world, translation studies, cognitive aspect.

Translation as a phenomenon of human activity plays an important role in the history and development of languages. Throughout the centuries, translation has mediated between cultures, facilitated the transfer of scientific knowledge, literary experience and spiritual values. Translation occupies a special place in linguistics because it reflects the complex processes of interrelationship of language systems and conceptual structures. This article analyses the significance of translation for linguistics, examines its functions, types and influence on linguistic theory.

Translation is a process of transferring the content of a text from one language to another, taking into account linguistic, cultural and pragmatic peculiarities. According to A.V. Fedorov, translation is «the transfer of a text by means of another language while preserving its semantic, stylistic and functional content» [1]. In this context, translation fulfils cognitive, communicative, cultural and cognitive functions.

Language is the main carrier of culture, and translation is a way of interaction between different cultures. Y.N. Naida notes that translation is «the transfer of meaning and spirit of the original» [2]. Translation allows not only to transfer information, but also to preserve cultural specificity, thus strengthening international ties.

From a linguistic point of view, translation is a complex process of interpretation and recoding. Modern translation studies are based on such disciplines as semantics, pragmatics, and cognitive linguistics. V.N. Komissarov's

research emphasises that translation requires analysis of both the linguistic level (lexicon, grammar) and the speech level (context, intention) [3].

The cognitive approach to translation considers it as a process of information processing in the translator's mind. According to T. Garvey, the translator works not only with language, but also with mental structures, forming a new interpretation of the text [4]. This includes conceptual metaphors, frames, scenarios and other elements of the cognitive structure of language.

Each language reflects a unique picture of the world. Translation allows correlating different language pictures, thus enriching and deepening their mutual understanding. G.V. Kolshansky emphasises that «translation is a window into another linguistic and cultural reality» [5]. It is especially important when translating texts saturated with national-cultural connotations.

Historically, translation has played an important role in the development of literary languages. For example, the translation of the Bible into Slavic languages (Cyril and Methodius) was the most important stage in the formation of the Old Slavic language [6]. Translations contributed to the enrichment of vocabulary, development of new genres and stylistic means.

There are many classifications of translation: by purpose (artistic, scientific, technical), by method (literal, semantic, adaptive), etc. Modern theories of translation (equivalence, scopos, functional adequacy) emphasise the purposes and functions of translation in a particular communication situation [7, 8].

Recently, machine translation and automatic translation have been actively developed. Despite technical progress, such systems are not yet capable of conveying the full range of meanings and cultural nuances, which makes a human translator indispensable. Research in this area shows that machine translation is particularly vulnerable to polysemy, idioms and context [9, 10].

Thus, translation is an integral part of linguistic science, fulfilling many functions and reflecting the complex processes of interaction between languages and cultures. It contributes to the dissemination of knowledge, the development of languages and the strengthening of intercultural dialogue. Translation requires a deep knowledge not only of language systems, but also of the cultural and cognitive context in which communication takes place. In the era of globalisation, the importance of translation as a scientific and practical discipline is only increasing.

Литература:

1. Фёдоров А. В. Основы общей теории перевода. — 3-е изд., испр. — СПб.: Изд-во Ленинградского гос. ун-та, 2002. — 208 с. — С. 15–34.

2. Комиссаров В. Н. Современное переводоведение: Учебник для вузов. — 4-е изд., стер. — М.: ЭТС, 2004. — 384 с. — С. 45-72.
3. Влахов С., Флорин С. Непереводимое в переводе. — М.: Международные отношения, 1980. — 320 с. — С. 102-125.
4. Швейцер А. Д. Теория перевода: Статус, проблемы, аспекты. — М.: Наука, 1988. — 216 с. — С. 51-78.
5. Рецкер Я. И. Теория перевода и переводческая практика. — М.: Международные отношения, 1974. — 200 с. — С. 29-46.
6. Алексеева И. С. Введение в переводоведение. — 6-е изд. — СПб.: Изд-во Златоуст, 2010. — 288 с. — С. 91-110.
7. Баркхад Н. И. Перевод как межъязыковая и межкультурная коммуникация // Вестник Московского университета. Серия 9. Филология. — 2012. — №5. — С. 89-95.
8. Латышев Л. К. Практика перевода (на материале английского и русского языков). — М.: Высшая школа, 1988. — 192 с. — С. 60-81.
9. Newmark P. A Textbook of Translation. — New York: Prentice Hall, 1988. — 292 p. — P. 95-117.
10. Nataly Kelly, Jost Zetzsche. Found in Translation: How Language Shapes Our Lives and Transforms the World. — New York: Perigee, 2012. — 288 p. — P. 67-83.

